

IN MEMORIAM
CORNELIU DINU
(1944-2020)

Danube Delta, 1999. Photo courtesy of Prof. How Kin WONG

Corneliu Dinu, a bright figure of Romanian Geology, of Romanian science, left us after a life dedicated to Geology and to teaching of young specialists. A life in which Cornel, let me call him so, because we were bound by a warm friendship for many decades, which was based on the identical understanding of the basic notions of life, of human duty, of fairness and honesty and of professional interests, tried to give everything to society, to build and shape young people and specialists for the good of the country.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4700323

Professor Corneliu Dinu's professional activity began in 1967 as a geological engineer at the Prospecting Enterprise. Since 1970, C. Dinu has worked in higher education, at the Institute of Oil, Gas and Geology, Faculty of Technical Geology, and then, after 1973, at the University of Bucharest, Faculty of Geology and Geophysics. He climbed the teaching ranks so that, in 1993, he became a full professor, and after 2010, a professor emeritus. He has conducted 25 PhD theses, of which 7 abroad with double coordination. From 1995 until now, he has been a member of the Academia Europaea. In 1985 he received the "Grigore Cobălcescu" award of the Romanian Academy.

For 14 years (from 1990 to 2003) he had been dean of the Faculty of Geology and Geophysics, during which time the faculty experienced, thanks to his efforts, a flourishing standing like no other, when its international fame reached peak. In the period 1996-2012, he was president of the Bucharest Geoscience Forum and contributed essentially to raising the Forum to the highest international level. He has been a member of prestigious international societies and professional associations such as the American Association of

Petroleum Geologists (AAPG) and the Society of Exploration Geophysicists.

Prof. C. Dinu was one of the most eminent Romanian specialists in the fields of Structural Geology, Tectonics, Seismotectonics and Sedimentary Basin Dynamics. He learned from and then continued the tradition of eminent scientists in the field of Earth Sciences, such as Ion Băncilă, Gheorghe Murgeanu, Ion Dumitrescu, Vasile Lăzărescu and others. He has also worked for oil companies, having an excellent expertise in analyzing the hydrocarbon potential of various regions in Romania, including the Black Sea.

Professor Corneliu Dinu collaborated with the specialized institutes – the National Institute of Marine Geology and Geoecology - GeoEcoMar and the Geological Institute of Romania, bringing his contribution of expertise and creative power to the activities of these institutions.

Prof. C. Dinu collaborated also with the Romanian Academy, with the Department of Geonomic Sciences, for contributing or making specialised analyses and documents, requested by the Government, documents regarding the evaluation of the country's energy potential, and the

completion or more judicious drafting of official documents (laws and government decisions and ordinances). The last document written by Corneliu Dinu for the Romanian Academy, was the chapter "Tectonics" of the History of Geosciences in Romania. The Department of Geonomic Sciences has always relied entirely on collaboration with Professor C. Dinu, as a highly qualified expert, with extensive experience and great honesty.

By the disappearance of Professor Corneliu Dinu, the Romanian Geosciences suffer a heavy and painful loss. It will be particularly difficult to replace his experience and

knowledge. But it is even harder to break up with our friend Corneliu Dinu, the man we have relied on and supported in all our activity and existence for over 50 years since life and profession have brought us closer.

Sorrowful thoughts, sorrowful condolences to the Dinu family, especially to his wife Laura and daughter Irina. All our thoughts go to them and I would like to assure them that we will keep Cornel in mind and heart forever.

God rest his soul !

Prof Dr Nicolae Panin
Member of the Romanian Academy

ARTICLES IN EXTENSO

- DINU C.**, (1971). Prezența faciesului cu Bositra buchi (Römer) în flancul estic al Sinclinalului Hăghimaș, la izvoarele Troțușului. *Bul. Soc. Științe Geol. R. S. România*, **XIII**: 21-27, București.
- DINU C.**, **MATEI V.**, (1972). Precizări asupra vârstei și poziției stratelor de Lunca din sinclinalul Hăghimaș. *St. cerc. geol., geogr., seria geol.*, **117(1)**: 419-424, București.
- TUDOR M.**, **DINU C.**, (1972). Notă asupra Miocenului superior din sinclinalul Predeal-Sărari. *Bul. IPGG*, **XVIII**: 39-44, București.
- DINU C.**, **SOFRON E.**, (1973). Analiza suprafețelor de tendință a pelitelor flișului cretacic inferior din bazinul Troțușului (Carpații Orientali). *Bul. IPGG*, **XX**: 33-40, București.
- LĂZĂRESCU V.**, **DINU C.**, (1973). Considerations neotectoniques sur l'avant-pays des Carpates en Moldavie du nord. *Rev. roum. geol., geophys., geogr., s.de geol.*, **117(2)**: 135-143, București.
- ZAMFIRESCU FL.**, **GRUJINSCHI C.**, **DINU C.**, **FODOREANU D.**, **SIMON A.**, **GEORGESCU O.**, **NICOLAU E.**, **HOSSU G.**, **DRUMEN C.**, **ULIAN A.**, (1975). Procesele de sufozie – factor principal în declanșarea alunecărilor de mare amploare din bazinul Văii Rîmna (Vrancea). *Lucr. Col. Nat. de Geomorfologie aplicată*: 143-152, Iași.
- GRUJINSCHI C.**, **ZAMFIRESCU FL.**, **DINU C.**, **FODOREANU D.**, **GEORGESCU O.**, **NICOLAU E.**, **HOSSU G.**, **SIMON A.**, **DRUMEN C.**, **ULIAN A.**, (1975). Alunecările de teren, factor activ în formarea și menținerea cuestelor din bazinul Văii Rîmna (Vrancea). *Lucr. Col. Naț. de Geomorfologie aplicată*: 153-160, Iași.
- DINU C.**, (1977). Compoziția granulometrică și distribuția sedimentelor actuale din lacul de baraj Bicaz. *Comunic. Sect. Geol. Univ. Buc. Ses. Științ. Festivă*: 307-320, București.
- GRUJINSCHI C.**, **ZAMFIRESCU FL.**, **DINU C.**, **FODOREANU E.**, **GEORGESCU C.**, **NICOLAU E.**, **HOSSU G.**, **SIMON A.**, **DRUMEN C.**, **ULIAN A.**, (1978). Quelques remarques sur le relief du type "cuesta" dans la Dépression morphologique Rîmna (Roumanie). *Ann. Soc. Géol. Belg.*, **100**: 175-181, Liège.
- MANOLIU E.**, **DRAGASTAN O.**, **DINU C.**, (1978). Contribution a la connaissance de la géologie du Mont Lespezi (Massif de Bucegi). *Anal. Univ. Buc.*, **XXVII**: 25-36, București.
- GRIGORESCU D.**, **DINU C.**, (1978). Aspecte sedimentologice și paleogeografice relevate de nisipurile cuarțoase bassarabiene din Dobrogea de Sud (zona Cobadin-Chirnoveni). *Anal. Univ. Buc.*, **XXVII**: 37-45, București.
- GRUJINSCHI C.**, **DINU C.**, **COSMA R.**, **FODOREANU E.**, **TRIMBIȚĂȘU M.**, **STANCIU A.**, **ZOMBORI W.**, **BURST A.**, **NEGUȚ D.**, **SIKO M.**, **STAMATE V.**, **ULIAN A.**, (1979). Distribution, composition et caractéristiques de la tranche superficielle de sédiments du lac du barrage Bicaz (Roumanie). *Ann. Soc. Geol. Belg.*, **101**: 55-66, Liège.
- ALMĂȘAN B.**, **LĂZĂRESCU V.**, **DINU C.**, **MERCUS D.**, (1980). Condiții stratigrafice și structurale de zăcământ ale antracitului și șisturilor pirofilitice din zona Viezuroiu. *Mine, petrol și gaze*, **131(8)**: 389-397, București.
- JIPA D.**, **DINU C.**, **MIHĂȘAN L.**, (1981). Evoluția texturală a aluviunilor Văii Cernei în sectorul cuprins între baraje hidrotehnice. *St. cerc. geol. geofiz., geogr., geologie*, **25(2)**: 263-273, București.
- LĂZĂRESCU V.**, **DINU C.**, (1981). Characteristic stages and formations of Romanian Eastern Carpathians evolution. *Carp.-Balk. Geol. Assoc., XII Congr., An. Inst. Geol. Geof.*, **LX**: 107-114, București.
- ZAMFIRESCU FL.**, **COMȘA R.**, **DINU C.**, **MATEI L.**, (1983). Structuri geotehnice caracteristice pe selful românesc al Mării Negre. *Lucr. științ. a V-a Conf. Naț. Geotehn. Fundații*, **II**: 448-453, Cluj Napoca.
- PAULIUC S.**, **PREDA L.**, **BĂDĂLUȚĂ A.**, **DINU C.**, **ȚINTILĂ L.**, **BARUS T.**, **CULDA V.**, **SERINI V.**, (1983). Nouvelles données concernant la géochimie et la genèse des dépôts bitumineux de la zone marginale des Flysch des Carpates Orientales dans les périmètres Tazlăul Mare et Buzău-Teleajen. *Anal. Univ. București, Geologie*, **XXXII**: 33-40, București.
- ALMĂȘAN B.**, **ZAMFIRESCU FL.**, **COMȘA R.**, **DINU C.**, **MATEI L.**, (1983). Sur les conditions géotechniques de la stabilité des plate-formes mobiles de forage marin sur la plate-forme continentale roumaine de la Mer Noire. *Carp.-Balk. Geol. Assoc., XII Congr., An. Inst. Geol. Geofiz.*, **LXIII**: 171-178, București.

- ZAMFIRESCU F., COMȘA R., **DINU C.**, MATEI L., (1984). Metodologii noi de investigare a terenurilor de fundare de pe șelful românesc al Mării Negre. *Rev. Mine, Petrol, Gaze*, **35**(3): 129-132, București.
- DINU C.**, (1985). Geologic study of the Cretaceous Flysch Deposits in the Upper Course of the Trotuș Valley (East Carpathians). *An. Inst. Geol. Geofiz.*, **XXV**: 1-135, București.
- DINU C.**, (1986). Observații sedimentologice în flîșul curbicortical din bazinul Trotușului (Carpații Orientali). *An. Maz. Șt. Nat. P. Neamț, Geol.-Geogr.*, **V**: 193-201, Piatra Neamț.
- MOCANU V.D., ZAMFIRESCU FL., **DINU C.**, MOLDOVEANU V., (1989). Implicațiile elementelor noi privind hidrogeologia Dobrogei de Sud în perspectiva creșterii debitelor exploatare pentru alimentarea cu apă a localităților. *Bul. Simpoz. Tehnica, ISLGC, Sinaia*.
- ZAMFIRESCU F., **DINU C.**, GRĂDINARU E., (1989). Tectonica Dobrogei de Sud. Simpoz. „Grigore Cobalcescu” Iași.
- DINU C.**, FRUNZESCU D., (1990). Stratonomi and sedimentologic analysis of the Podu Morii Beds Formation from the Văleni Spur Oligocene (East Carpathians). *Anal. Univ. Buc.*, **XXXIX**: 58-68, București.
- MOCANU V., RĂDULESCU FL., **DINU C.**, (1991). Lithospheric structure of Romania and recent crustal movements. Geodynamic connections. *Rev. Roum. Géol. Géogr., Géophys., Géophysique*, **35**: 1-11, București.
- DINU C.**, CALOTĂ C., MOCANU V., CIULAVU D., (1991). Geotectonic setting and the particular structural features of the Beiuș Basin, on the basis of geological and geophysical data synthesis. *Rev. Roum. Géophysique*, **35**: 77-87, Bucharest.
- ZAMFIRESCU FL., **DINU C.**, (1991). Processes and mechanics specific to the beginning and evolution of the landslides in the Râmna Valley - Vrancea Basin. *Lucr. simp. Național pentru alunecări de teren*, **6**, Piatra Neamț.
- GEORGESCU O., FRUNZESCU D., **DINU C.**, (1992). Recherches minéralogiques et pétrographiques sur les niveaux cineritiques dans l'éperon de Văleni. *A V-a Conf. Naț. a Grupului român pentru studiul argilelor, București*, 1988, Vol. Spec.: 47-62, București.
- RĂDULESCU FL., NACU V., BITER M., **DINU C.**, MOCANU V., (1992). Recent crustal movements in the Vrancea seismic region (România). *Proceedings General Assembly of the European Sismological Commission*, **XXII**: 349-352.
- GEORGESCU P., **DINU C.**, NICULESCU V., ION D., (1993). Some applications of VES to groundwater exploration in the vicinity of the Romanian coast of the Black Sea. *Rev. Roum. Géophysique*, **37**: 113-121, Bucharest.
- GEORGESCU P., **DINU C.**, NICULESCU V., ION D., MOGOȘ S., (1993). Determination of the hydrogeological and geotechnical conditions of the Slănic Prahova salt massif (Romania) by electrical prospecting. *Rev. Roum. Géophysique*, **37**: 105-112.
- WONG H.K., PANIN N., **DINU C.**, GEORGESCU P., RAHN C., (1994). Morphology and post-chaudian (Late Pleistocene) evolution of the submarine Danube fan complex. *Terra Nova*, **6**: 502-511.
- NEGUȚ A., **DINU C.**, SAVU L., BARDAN R., NEGUȚ M.L., CRAICIU I., (1994). Stress orientation determination in Romania by borehole breakouts. Geodynamic significance. *Rev. Roum. Géophysique*: 45-56, Bucharest.
- CIULAVU D., BERTOTTI G., ANDRIESEN P., CLOETINGH S., **DINU C.**, HUISMANS R., SANDERS C., (1994). Tectonics of the Transylvania Basin. *Rom. J. Tecton. Reg. Geol.*, **75** (suppl. 1): 7-8, București.
- ZAMFIRESCU FL., MOLDOVEANA V., PITU N., **DINU C.**, NASH H., (1995). Vulnerability to Pollution of Karst Aquifer in Southern Dobrogea. *Proceedings of the International Hydrological Symposium. "Impact of Activities on Groundwater"*, Constanța, mai 1995.
- MOCANU V., **DINU C.**, HEINZ H., RĂDULESCU F., DIACONESCU C., DIACONESCU M., POMPILIAN A., (1995). Seismological particularities of the Romanian crust. *Rom. J. Tecton. Reg. Geol.*, **75** (suppl. 1): 38-39, București.
- NEGUȚ A., **DINU C.**, LUȚAC D., (1995). Faciesuri de tip "channel-fill" identificate pe baza diagramei geofizice, cu exemplificări pe structurile Lebăda și Sinoe (Seiful Mării Negre). *St. cerc. geofizică*, **33**: 69-75, București.
- DANIELESCU-CHIRLOMEZ C., UNGUREANU V.G., STANICĂ A., GAIȚĂ C., PANIN N., **DINU C.**, FĂRNOAGĂ D., (1995). Geological study of the Black Sea shore erosion processes in front of the Danube Delta. In: Evolution and environmental safeguard of the Dobrogea coastal zone (Black Sea). Instituto di Geologia Marina, Bologna, *Rapp. Tecn.*, **41**:12-21.
- DINU C.**, MORARIU D.C., MOCANU V., (1996). Hydrocarbon resources of România -an overview. In: Wessely G. & Leibl W. (Eds.), "Oil and Gas in Alpidic Thrustbelts and Basins of Central and Eastern Europe". *EAGE Spec. Publ.*, **5**: 23-27.
- MOCANU V., **DINU C.**, RĂDULESCU F.L., DIACONESCU M., DIACONESCU C., POMPILIAN A., (1996). Seismogeological features of the crust in România. In: Wessely G. & Leibl W. (eds.) "Oil and Gas in Alpidic Thrustbelts and Basins of Central and Eastern Europe". *EAGE Sp. Publ.*, **5**: 289-299.
- HUISMANS R.S., BERTOTTI G., CIULAVU D., SANDERS C.A.E., CLOETINGH S., **DINU C.**, (1997). Structural evolution of the Transilvanian Basin (România): a sedimentary basin in the bend zone of the Carpathians. In: Neubauer F., Cloetingh S., **DINU C.**, MOCANU V. (Eds.). Tectonics of the Alpine-Carpathian-Pannonian region: II. *Tectonophysics*, **272**: 269-290.
- MAȚENCO L., ZOETEMEIJER R., CLOETINGH S., **DINU C.**, (1997). Lateral variation in the mechanical properties of the Romanian external Carpathians: inferences of flexure and gravity modelling. *Tectonophysics*, **282**: 147-166.
- MAȚENCO L., BERTOTTI G., **DINU C.**, CLOETINGH S., (1997). Tertiary tectonic evolution of the external south Carpathians and the adjacent Moesian platform (Romania). *Tectonics*, **16**(6): 896-911.
- NEUBAUER F., CLOETINGH S., **DINU C.**, MOCANU V., (1997). Tectonics of the Alpino-Pannonian-Carpathian region: Introduction. *Tectonophysics*, **272** (2-4): 93-97.
- WINGUTH C., WONG H.K., PANIN N., **DINU C.**, GEORGESCU P., UNGUREANU V.G., (1997). Upper Quaternary sea level changes in Northwestern Black Sea, Preliminary results. Proc. Internat. Workshop on „Fluvial Marine Interactions” in Malnaș, România, oct. 1-7, 1996. *Geo-Eco-Marina*, **2**: 102-114.
- WONG H.K., WINGUTH C., PANIN N., **DINU C.**, WOLLSCHLAGER M., GEORGESCU P., UNGUREANU V.G., KRUGLIAKOV V.V., PODSHUVEIT V., (1997). The Danube and Dniepr Fans: morphostructure and evolution. Proc. Internat. Workshop on “Fluvial Marine Interactions” in Malnaș, România, oct. 1-7, 1996. *Geo-Eco-Marina*, **2**: 77-101.

- CIULAVU D., **DINU C.**, DIACONESCU V., (1998). Late Miocene to Pliocene Kinematics of the South-Western Part of the Transylvanian Basin. In: **Dinu C.** & Mocanu V. (Eds). Geological Structure and Hydrocarbon Potential of the Romanian Areas., *BGF special volume, 1*: 70-84.
- CIULAVU D., **DINU C.**, (1998). The Transilvanian Basin. In: CERGOP Monograph of Southern Carpathians”, Warsaw University of Technology: 111-126.
- MAȚENCO L., BERTOTTI G., **DINU C.**, CLOETINGH S., (1998). Tectonic Evolution of the Contact Zone Between the South Carpathians and the Adjacent Moesian Platform. In: **Dinu C.** & Mocanu V. (Eds.). Geological Structure and Hydrocarbon Potential of the Romanian Areas, *BGF special volume, 1*: 85-121.
- FLOOD R.D., RYAN W.B.F., WONG H.K., PANIN N., LERICOLAIS G., BERNE S., **DINU C.**, SHIMKUS K.M., (1999). Deep sea drilling program in the Black Sea. Climate change and sedimentation in the Black Sea region in response to Pleistocene climatic cycles: letter of intent. *CIESM Workshop Series, 6*, Granada.
- JIPA D., **DINU C.**, MARINESCU N., (1999). Sedimentological significance of subsurface data in the Western Dacian Basin (Upper Neogene, România): sedimentary environments, genetic sequence, basinal evolution. In: Proc. Intern. Workshop on „Modern and Ancient Sedimentary Environments and processes”, Moeciu, Romania, Oct. 1998. *Geo-Eco-Marina, 4*: 147-153.
- MOCANU V., RUSSO R., WENZEL F., **DINU C.**, FLOWER M., (2000). *Seismic attenuation in the Vrancea region, Carpathians, România*. Bucharest International Geophysical Conference and Exposition, *Conference volume, SEG/EAGE/RSG*: 264-267.
- DIACONESCU C., MOCANU V., RAILEANU V., **DINU C.**, MATENCO L., PRODEHL C., HAUSER F., WENZEL F., (2000). Active subduction or determination lithosphere - Structure of the Southeast Carpathian orogen, Romania. AGU Fall Meeting, Nov. 28, 2000, F1090, T52A-21. *EOS Transactions, 81*(48).
- WENZEL F., **DINU C.**, SPERNER B., HETTEL S., LORENZ F., FUCHS K., FRIEDRICHS J., MOCANU V., (2000). From upper mantle tomography to hazard assessment - the Vrancea example. AGU Fall Meeting, Nov. 28, 2000, F1222, T21E-02, *EOS Transactions, 81*(48).
- CIULAVU D., **DINU C.**, SZAKACS A., DORDEA D., (2000). Neogene kinematics of the Transilvania Basin (România). *AAPG Bulletin, 84*(10): 1589-1615.
- WINGUTH C., WONG H.K., PANIN N., **DINU C.**, GEORGESCU P., UNGUREANU G., KRUGLIAKOV V.V., PODSHUVEIT V., (2000). Upper Quaternary water level history and sedimentation in the northwestern Black Sea. *Marine Geology, 167*: 127-146.
- FLOWER M., MOCANU V., ZONGJIN M., RUSSO R., YEM N.T., CHI C.T., CUONG N.Q., JINFU D., DILEK Y., **DINU C.**, FUTIAN L., LIU M., HOANG N., ROBINSON P., XUANGXEI M., PUNONGBAYAN R., WENZEL F., YUMUL G., WINDOM E., (2001). Project Targets Mantle Dynamics and Tethyan Hazard Mitigation. *EOS Transactions, American Geophysical Union, 81*(49): 600-608.
- CIULAVU D., **DINU C.**, CLOETINGH S., (2002). Late Cenozoic Tectonic Evolution of the Transylvanian Basin and Northeastern Part of the Pannonian Basin: Constraints from Seismic Profiling and Numerical Modelling. *EGU Stephan Mueller Special Publication Series, 3*: 105-120.
- DINU C.**, WONG H.K., ȚAMBREA D., (2002). Stratigraphic and tectonic synthesis of the Romanian Black Sea shelf and correlation with major land structure. In: **Dinu C.** & Mocanu V. (Eds). Geology and tectonics of the Romanian Black Sea shelf and its hydrocarbon potential. *BGF special volume, 2*: 101-117.
- HAUSER F., PRODEHL C., LANDES M., BALA A., RAILEANU V., BRIBACH I., KNAPP J., DIACONESCU C., **DINU C.**, MOCANU V., FIELTZ W., HARDER S., KELLER R.G., HEGHEDUS E., STEPHENSON R.A., (2002). Seismic experiments target earthquake-region in Romania. *EOS, 83*: 41.
- WONG H.K., LUDEMANN T., PANIN N., KONERDING P., **DINU C.**, (2002). Northwestern Black Sea: Upper Quaternary water level and sedimentation. In: Mediterranean and Black Sea Turbidite Systems and Deep-sea-fans., Bucharest 5-8 June 2002, CIESM Workshop series no. **17**: 85-89.
- ȚAMBREA D., **DINU C.**, SÂNPETREAN E., (2002). Characteristics of the tectonics and lithostratigraphy of the Black Sea shelf, offshore România. In: **Dinu C.** & Mocanu V. (Eds), Geology and tectonics of the Romanian Black Sea shelf and its hydrocarbon potential. *BGF special volume, 2*: 29-42.
- POPESCU I., LERICOLAIS G., PANIN N., DROZ L., WONG H.K., **DINU C.**, (2002). Architecture and recent sedimentary evolution of the Danube deep-sea fan (Black Sea). In: CIESM Workshop Series 17. Turbidite systems and deep-sea fans of the Mediterranean and the Black Seas, Monaco/2002, INCD GEOECOMAR: 81-84.
- CLOETINGH S., HORVATH F., **DINU C.**, STEPHENSON R.A., BERTOTTI G., BADA G., MATENCO L., GARCIA-CASTELLANOS D., (2003). Probing tectonic topography in the aftermath of continental convergence in Central Europe. *EOS Transactions. AGU, 84*(10-11): 89-93
- GILLET H., LERICOLAIS G., REHAULT J.L., **DINU C.**, (2003). La stratigraphie oligo-miocene et la surface d'érosion messinienne en Mer Noire, stratigraphie sismique haute resolution. *C.R. Geoscience, 335*(12): 907-916.
- MAȚENCO L., BERTOTTI G., CLOETINGH S., **DINU C.**, (2003). Subsidence analysis and tectonic evolution of the external Carpathian-Moesian Platform region during Neogene times. *Sedimentary Geology, 156*(1-4): 71 -94.
- DINU C. ET AL.**, (2003). Transition from Extensional to Compressional Structure in the Upper Miocene Shally Deposits, Western Black Sea. *AAPG International Conference, Barcelona, Spain, Sept. 2003, Conference Paper*: DOI: 10.13140/2.1.4172.5440
- POPESCU I., LERICOLAIS G., PANIN N., NORMAND A., **DINU C.**, LE DREZEN E., (2004). The Danube submarine canyon (Black Sea) : morphology and sedimentary processes. *Marine Geology, 206*: 249-265.
- TĂRĂPOANĂ M., GARCIA-CASTELLANOS D., BERTOTTI G., MATENCO L., CLOETINGH S., **DINU C.**, (2004). Role of the 3D distributions of load and lithospheric strength in orogenic axes: polystage subsidence in the Carpathians foredeep. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters, 221*(1-4): 1-18.
- TĂRĂPOANĂ M., MAȚENCO L., BERTOTTI G., **DINU C.**, CLOETINGH S., (2004). Architecture of the Focșani Depression: a very deep basin in the Carpathians bend (România). *Tectonics, 22*(6): 1-17

- DIMITRIU R.G., **DINU C.**, SAVA C.S., ȚAMBREA D., (2004). Deep Geotectonic Controls Revealed by Geophysical Potential Data on the Romanian Offshore. *AAPG European Region Conference with GSA Prague*, October 10-13.
- STAN A., **DINU C.**, RĂILEANU A., (2004). Tectonic control on oil fields distribution in Central Part of the Moesian Platform. In: **DINU C.** & Mocanu V. (Eds.). *Geology, Tectonics and Hydrocarbon Potential of the Romanian Moesian Platform. BGF Special Volume, 3*: 23-30.
- MĂTREȘU J., **DINU C.**, (2004). Paleozoic extensional basins in the Western Part of the Moesian Platform. In: **DINU C.** & Mocanu V. (Eds.). *Geology, Tectonics and Hydrocarbon Potential of the Romanian Moesian Platform. BGF Special Volume, 3*: 63-70.
- CLOETINGH S., MAȚENCO L., BADA G., **DINU C.**, MOCANU V., (2005). The evolution of the Carpathians-Pannonian system: Interaction between neotectonics, deep structure, polyphase orogeny and sedimentary basins in a source to sink natural laboratory. *Tectonophysics, 410*: 1-14.
- DINU C.**, WONG H.K., ȚAMBREA D., MAȚENCO L., (2005). Stratigraphy and structural characteristics of the Romanian Black Sea shelf. *Tectonophysics, 410*: 417-435.
- KNAPP J.H., KNAPP C.C., RĂILEANU V., MAȚENCO L., MOCANU V., **DINU C.**, (2005). Crustal constraints of the origin of mantle seismicity in the Vrancea zone, Romania: The case for active continental lithospheric delamination. *Tectonophysics, 410*: 311-323.
- DINU C.**, MOLDOVEANU T., DIACONESCU V., MAȚENCO L., (2005). Seismotectonics of the foreland of the Romanian Carpathians characterization of seismic sources and insights on seismic hazard analysis. *Journal of the Balkan Geophysical Society, 8(1)*: 727- 730.
- DINU C.**, ȚAMBREA D., RĂILEANU A., (2005). Structural characteristics, seismic facies and depositional framework of Eocene deposits, in Central Romanian Black Sea offshore. *Journal of the Balkan Geophysical Society, 8(1)*: 373 -376.
- MĂTREȘU J., RĂILEANU V., **DINU C.**, (2005). Relationships between tectonic elements and crustal reflectivity – A case from Moesian Platform. *Journal of the Balkan Geophysical Society, 8(1)*: 125-128.
- RĂILEANU V., HAUSER F., FIELITZ W., **DINU C.**, BALA A., LANDES M., PRODEHL C., (2005). A Transilvania crustal structure model from the North Dobrogea through Vrancea region to the Western. *Journal of the Balkan Geophysical Society, 8(1)*: 299-302.
- DINU C.**, JIPA D., (2005). General geological and hydrogeological data from the Oil Terminal Constanta area. *Geo-Eco-Marina, 7-8*: 20-23.
- JIPA D., ALBU M., **DINU C.**, PAVEL A., (2005). Hydrocarbon contamination inside Oil Terminal North-1 Storage Area – Summary and data interpretation. *Geo-Eco-Marina, 7-8*: 60-67.
- JIPA D., ALBU M., **DINU C.**, PAVEL A. 2005. Hydrocarbon contamination east of Oil Terminal North-1 Storage Area – Summary and data interpretation. *Geo-Eco-Marina, 7-8*: 87-90.
- CLOETINGH S., BADA., MAȚENCO L., LANKRAEJER A., HORVATH F., **DINU C.**, (2006). Modes of basin (de)formation, lithospheric strength and vertical motions in the Pannonian-Carpathian system: inferences from thermo-mechanical modelling. In: Stephenson R.A. & Gee D. (Eds.). *European Lithosphere Dynamics. Geological Society of London, Memoirs, 32*: 207-221.
- MAȚENCO L., BERTOTTI G., LEEVER K., CLOETINGH S., SCHMID S.M., TĂRĂPOANCA M., **DINU C.**, (2007). Large-scale deformation in a locked collisional boundary: interplay between subsidence and uplift, intraplate stress and inherited lithospheric structure in the late stage of the SE Carpathian evolution. *Tectonics, 26(4)*: 1-29.
- HAUSER F., RĂILEANU V., FIELITZ W., **DINU C.**, LANDES M., BALA., PRODEHL C., (2007). Seismic crustal structure between the Transylvanian Basin and the Black Sea. *Tectonophysics, 430*:1-25.
- RĂILEANU V., HAUSER F., BALA A., FIELITZ W., PRODEHL C., **DINU C.**, LANDES M., (2007). Deep seismic sounding across the Vrancea Region. Intern. *Symposium on Strong Vrancea Earthquakes and Risk Mitigation*, Oct. 4-6, 2007, Bucharest, Romania: 80-86.
- RĂILEANU V., BALA A., **DINU C.**, RADULIAN M., POPESCU E., DIACONESCU V., MATECIUC D., POPA , (2007). Crustal seismicity and deep structure in the SE Carpathians and its foreland. Intern. *Symposium on Strong Vrancea Earthquakes and Risk Mitigation*, Oct. 4- 6, (2007), Bucharest, Romania: 87-90.
- CLOETINGH S., ZIEGLER P.A., BOGAARD P.J.F., ANDRIESEN P.A.M., ARTEMIeva I.M., BADA G., VAN BALEN R.T., BEEKMAN F., BEN-AVRAHAM Z., BRUN J.P., TESAURO M., THIEKEN A., TIMAR G., TOTHL., VAN ENST J., VAN WEES J.D., VARGA G., WEBER Z., WILSON M., WOLF D., **DINU C.**, (2007). TOPO-EUROPE: The geoscience of coupled deep Earth-surface processes. *Global and Planetary Change, 58*: 1-118.
- SHNUKOV E.F., PANIN N.S., **DINU C.**, MASLAKOV N.A., PARYSHEV A.A., (2008). Gas volcanism in the Romania. The paper 1. *Geology and mineral resources of world ocean, 3*: 90-102, Kiev.
- SHNUKOV E.F., PANIN N.S., **DINU C.**, KUTNY V.A., MASLAKOV N.A., (2008). Gas volcanism in the Romania. The paper 2. Mineralogy of Piclele Mari and Piclele Mici Mud Volcanoes. *Geology and mineral resources of world ocean, 4*: 29-39, Kiev.
- SCHNIUKOV E.F., PANIN N.S., **DINU C.**, KUTNIY V.A., MASLAKOV N.A., (2009). Mud-volcanoes of Romania. Preliminary data on the mineralogy of Păcelele Mari and Păcelele Mici Mud-volcanoes. *Geo-Eco-Marina, 15*: 131-138.
- RĂILEANU V., **DINU C.**, ARDELEANU L., DIACONESCU V., POPESCU E., BALA A., (2009). Crustal seismicity and associated fault system in Romania. *Proceedings of the 27-th ECGS Workshop: Seismicity patterns in Euro-Med. Region, Luxemburg, 17-19 Nov. 2008. In: Cahier du Centre Europeean de Geodynamique et de seismologie, 153-159. ISBN 9-7829-19-89702-5*
- KONERDING C., **DINU C.**, WONG H.K., (2010). Seismic sequence stratigraphy, structure and Mio-Pleistocene subsidence history of the Romanian Black Sea shelf. In: Sosson M., Kaymakci N., Stephenson R., Bergerat F. & Starostenko V. (Eds.) *Sedimentary basin tectonics from the Black Sea and Caucasus to the Arabian Platform. Geological Society of London, Special Publications 210(340)*:159-180.
- MUNTEANU I., MAȚENCO L., **DINU C.**, CLOETINGH S., (2011). Kinematics of back-arc inversion of the Western Black Sea Basin. *Tectonics, 30(5)*: 1-2.
- NICOLESCU O., **DINU C.**, (2012). Thickness variation of levees Danube submarine channel in the bifurcation area to the channel complex from the mid-Danube fan (Black Sea). *12th International Multidisciplinary Scientific GeoConference and EXPO - Modern Management of Mine Producing, Geology and Environmental Protection, SGEM 2012*

- MUNTEANU I., MAȚENCO L., DINU C., CLOETINGH S., (2012). Effects of large sea-level variations in connected basins: the Dacian–Black Sea system of the Eastern Paratethys. *Basin Research*, **24**(5): 583– 597.
- NECEA D., KADEREIT A., MATENCO L., FIELTZ W., ANDRIESEN P.A.M., DINU C., (2013). Middle Pleistocene to Holocene fluvial terrace development and uplift-driven valley incision in SE Carpathians, Romania. *Tectonophysics*, **602**: 332–354, TOPO-EUROPE III.
- MUNTEANU I., WILLINGSHOFER E., MAȚENCO L., DINU C., (2013). Transfer of deformation in back-arc basins with a laterally variable rheology: Constraints from analogue modelling of the Balkanides – Western Black Sea inversion. *Tectonophysics*, **602**: 223-236 TOPO-EUROPE III.
- TILIȚĂ M., MAȚENCO L., DINU C., IONESCU L., CLOETINGH S., (2013). Understanding the kinematic evolution and genesis of a back-arc continental “sag” basin: The Neogene evolution of the Transylvanian Basin, *Tectonophysics*, **602**: 237-258.
- MAȚENCO L., ANDRIESEN P.A.M., AVRAM C., BADA G., BEEKMAN F., BIELIK M., TER BORGH M., CIFICI G., CVETKOVIĆ V., DINU C., STEPHENSON R., STOVBA S., SOKOUTIS D., STANKOVIANSKY M., STOICA M., STOJADINOVIC U., TOLIĆ M., TOMLIJENOVIC B., TER VOORDE M., WONG H.K., (2013). Quantifying the mass transfer from mountain ranges to deposition in sedimentary basins: Source to sink studies in the Danube Basin – Black Sea system. *Global and planetary change*, **103**: 1-18.
- MUNTEANU I., MAȚENCO L., IUSCO G., DINU C., CLOETINGH S., (2014). Tectonics of the Western Black Sea back-arc basin as revealed by the architecture of its sedimentary fill. *Conference paper, AAPG Conference*, Barcelona
- MAȚENCO L., MUNTEANU I., TER BORGH M., STANICĂ A., TILIȚĂ M., LERICOLAIS G., DINU C., OAIE G., (2015). The interplay between tectonics, sediment dynamics and gateways evolution in the Danube system from the Pannonian Basin to the western Black Sea. *Science of the Total Environment*, **543**: 802-827.
- BALA A., RAILEANU V., DINU C., DIACONESCU M., (2015). Crustal seismicity and active fault systems in Romania. *Romanian Reports in Physics*, **67**(3):1176-1191.
- DIMITRIU R.G., DINU C., (2015). Modelarea 23/4 a datelor gravimetrice și magnetimetrice marine pentru stabilirea alcătuirii petrografice a Ridicării C, evidențiată de seismica 3D în largul țărmlui românesc al Mării Negre. *Ses. Anuala de Comunicări științifice a INCD GeoEcoMar București*, 16 dec. 2015.
- DINU C., (2015). Domeniul marin – sursa de energie si resurse minerale. In: Hera C. (Ed.) *Schimbări climatice globale. Grijă pentru resurse Minerale*. Ed. Acad. Rom.: 209-218.3
- POPA M., OROS E., DINU C., RADULIAN M., BORLEANU F., ROGOZEA M., MUNTEANU I., NEAGOE C., (2016). The 2013 Earthquake Swarm in the Galati Area: First Results for a Seismotectonic Interpretation. In: Vacareanu R. & Ionescu C. (Eds.). *The 1940 Vrancea Earthquake. Issues, Insights and Lessons Learnt Proceedings of the Symposium Commemorating 75 Years from November 10, 1940 Vrancea Earthquake. Springer Natural Hazards*: 253-267.
- DIMITRIU R., DINU C., MUNTEANU I., STANCIU I., (2016). Potential data interpretation and 23/4 modelling aiming to decipher an elevated structure revealed by 3D seismic on the Romanian offshore. *16th International Multidisciplinary Scientific GeoConference SGEM*, 2016 Varna, Bulgaria: 499-510. DOI:10.13140/RG.2.1.4830.3603
- DIMITRIU R.G., DINU C., STANCIU I., (2016). 2¾D modelling of gravity and magnetic data in support of geologic interpretation of an elevated structure revealed by 3D seismics on the Romanian offshore. *AAPG Europe Region: European Regional Conference & Exhibition*, 19th-20th May, 2016, Bucharest, Romania
- NICOLESCU O., DINU C., (2016). Thickness estimation of the Danube submarine fan deep water deposits resulted from seismic sections (Black Sea). *16th International Multidisciplinary Scientific GeoConference SGEM 2016*, Albena, Bulgaria.
- SAVA C.S., DUDU A., ANGHEL S., DINU C., SOARE R., BURLACU A., ALEXE I., CHIRAN M., (2017). Multimodal transport of CO₂ for implementing CCUS in Romania. *Geo-Eco-Marina*, **23**: 223-227.
- MUNTEANU I., DIVIACCO P., SAULI C., DINU C., BURCA M., PANIN N., BRANCATELLI G., (2017). New insights into the Black Sea Basin, in the light of the reprocessing of vintage regional seismic data. In: Finkl C.W. & Makowski C. (Eds). *Diversity in Coastal Marine Sciences, Coastal Research Library*, **23**, DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-57577-3_6
- NICOLESCU O., DINU C., (2017). Mass transport complex in the basin floor environment of the danube submarine fan, Western Black Sea. *International Multidisciplinary Scientific GeoConference Surveying Geology and Mining Ecology Management*, SGEM 2017.
- DINU C., MUNTEANU I., ȚAMBREA D., PANIN N., (2018). Gas Hydrates, Flares Seeps Offshore Romania, A Review. *Geo-Eco-Marina* **24**: 5-54.
- LUDMANN T., WONG H.K., DINU C., BARISTEAS N., PANIN N., (2018). Characterisation of gas hydrates and free gas occurrences in the North-West Black Sea. *Rev. Roum. Géologie*, **61-62**: 31-43, București.
- ALEXE I., CHIRAN M., SAVA C.Ș., DUDU A., ANGHEL S., BURLACU A., DINU C., SOARE R., (2018). Utilization of captured CO₂ for implementing CCUS in Romania. *Geo-Eco-Marina*, **24**: 133-137
- TRAȘCĂ-CHIRIȚĂ N., ALEXE I., CHIRAN M., PROCA A., SAVA C.S., DUDU A.C., ANGHEL S., BURLACU A., DINU C., (2018). Injection and storage of CO₂ – Efficient method for increasing oil recovery. *Geo-Eco-Marina*, **24**: 139-143.
- POPA M., MUNTEANU I., BORLEANU F., OROS E., RADULIAN M., DINU C., (2018). Active tectonic deformation and associated earthquakes: a case study – South West Carpathians Bend zone. *Acta Geodaetica et Geophysica*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40328-018-0224-1>
- DINU C., (2018). Tectonica. In: Rădulescu D., Panin N., Anastasiu N., Brustur T. (Coord.) *Istoria geostiințelor în România. Stiințele geologice*: 290-314, Ed. Acad. Rom., București.
- DINU C., (2018). Ludovic Mrazec și geologia petrolului. *Academica*, Anul XXVIII, **333-334**: 90-97, București.

BOOKS

DINU C., (1985). Geologic study of the Cretaceous flysch deposits in the upper course of the Troțuș Valley (East Carpathians). *An. Inst. Geol. Geofiz.*, **XXV**: 1-135. Premiul “Grigore Cobalcescu” al Academiei Romane pe anul 1985

PAULIUC S., DINU C., (1985). Geologie structurală. Ed. Tehnică, București, 340 p.

DINU C., PAULIUC S., BARUS T., (1988). Geologie structurală – Lucrări practice. Tipografia Universității București, 208 p.

DINU C., MAȚENCO L., DIACONESCU V., MUNTEANU I., (2007). Analiza bazinelor de sedimentare. Ed. Vergiliu, București, 377 p.

FIELD TRIPS

WONG H.K., **DINU C.,** LÜDMANN T., (1996). Geological Field Trip "Romanian East Carpathians", 15-28 August 1996, Univ. București, 100 p.

BUTAC A., **DINU C.,** GRADINARU E., OLARU R., SERINIV., ȘINDILAR V., ȚAMBREA D., (1998). Field trip Dobrodja and Eastern Carpathian Bend Area, Romania, 16-18 sept. 1998., 120 p.

DINU C., WONG H.K., (2000). Geological Field Trip Guide - Field Trip to the South Carpathians, Summer Semester 2000, 70 p.

KLAMMER W., **DINU C.,** DOBRE S., NEDELCU E., STOICESCU AL., IONESCU G., (2006). Region East E&R – The Eastern Carpathians Field Trip, Romania, 24-27 mai 2006, 90 p.

WONG H.K., **DINU C.,** (2006). Geological Field Trip Guide - Field Trip to the South Carpathians, Summer Semester 2006, 123 p.

DINU C., GRADINARU E., STOICA M., DIACONESCU V., (2007). Dobrogea 2007 Field Trip Preparation and Assistance. PETROM SA – Member of OMV Group, 126 p.

BOOK CHAPTERS

DINU C., (2009). Neogene and Quaternary tectonic evolution of the western Black Sea Basin. *In:* Panin N., **Dinu C.,** Jipa D.C. (2009). TOPO – EUROPE SUMMER SCHOOL On Carpathian – Danube Delta Black Sea sedimentary systems, Murighiol, (2009), September 25th - October 10th, *Geo-Eco-Marina*, **spec. vol.:** 39-70.

DINU C., (1988). Rezolvarea accidentelor tectonice întâlnite în cursul deschiderii, pregătirii și exploatării zăcămintelor. *In:* Manualul inginerului de mine, **IV:** 213-346, Ed. Tehnică, București.

